

Description of the GeoServer style for bathymetry grids within DataHub

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Introduction

Purpose and Scope

This technical paper provides a step-by-step guide to replicating a bathymetry grid style using open-source tools, with a focus on QGIS and GeoServer. The primary audience includes data engineers, data scientists, and geoinformatics professionals with basic knowledge of GIS software.

The purpose of this guide is to document the technical process of style creation to enable reconstruction with widely available tools. The emphasis is on practical implementation rather than a scientific exploration of colour ramps or their perceptual properties. For readers interested in the theoretical aspects of colour ramps, publications by Cramer, Shephard, and Heron (2020), as well as Gołębiowska and Çöltekin (2022), provide valuable insights.

This guide addresses the following challenges:

- Extracting styles from ArcGIS to use in open-source software,
- Resolving compatibility issues between red, green, blue (RGB) images and float rasters, and
- Adapting styles for use within the limitations of GeoServer.

By focusing on practical solutions, this article aims to contribute to the growing body of open-source methodologies for geospatial data visualisation.

Background

Colour ramps used for bathymetric grids vary significantly. For instance, grid layers on the IHO DCDB Viewer¹ reveal different approaches across countries. Previously, the Marine Data Viewer² used the 'haxby' (fig. 1) and 'GMT_haxby' (fig. 2) colour ramps, both of which belong to the rainbow-like category.

Figure 1: 'haxby' is a continuous colour ramp with 10 segments (GRASS Development Team 2009)

¹https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/maps/iho_dcdb/

²<https://marine-data.de/?site=home>

Figure 2: 'GMT_haxby' is a discrete colour ramp with 32 segments (Wessel, Smith, and Trawoeger 2012)

To ensure consistency for the bathymetry grid layers on the Marine Data Viewer, a style similar to NOAA NCEI's ArcGIS-based 'haxby' colour ramp (fig. 3) was adopted. This style is used, for example, in the ArcGIS image service 'Multibeam Bathymetry Mosaic'³. The decision was influenced by the integration of the Marine Data Viewer's Web Map Services (WMS) into the IHO DCDB Viewer, hosted by NOAA NCEI. For simplicity, this guide refers to this colour ramp as 'NCEI_haxby'.

Figure 3: NOAA NCEI 'haxby' colour ramp (source: https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/maps/bathymetry/images/haxby_color_scale_8000-0.png)

Method

Overview

The process of creating a consistent bathymetry grid style using open-source tools and software includes three main steps:

- **Extracting Styles from ArcGIS:**
The colour ramp was retrieved from a raster function template (*.rft.xml) containing hue, saturation, and value (HSV) codes.
- **Recreating the Style in QGIS:**
A new colour ramp was manually created in QGIS using the extracted HSV codes, with adjustments made to visually match NOAA NCEI's ArcGIS image service.
- **Exporting and Implementing Styles in GeoServer:**
The final style was exported from QGIS in the Styled Layer Descriptor (SLD) format and adapted for use in GeoServer. Limitations in the SLD format and GeoServer styling required additional manual adjustments.

³https://gis.ngdc.noaa.gov/arcgis/rest/services/multibeam_mosaic/ImageServer

Software

The following tools were used in the workflow:

- ArcGIS Pro 3.0.0: For extracting the original style.
- QGIS 3.22.14: For recreating and adjusting the style.
- GeoServer 2.21.0 and 2.21.1: For implementing the final style and publishing the Web Map Service (WMS).

Extracting Styles from ArcGIS

NOAA NCEI's bathymetry style was originally created in ArcGIS using a custom colour ramp. However, ArcGIS Pro does not provide a direct way to export styles in a format compatible with open-source software like QGIS or GeoServer.

To extract the colour ramp, the NOAA NCEI's workflow was provided as a raster function template (*.rft.xml). Within it, colours are stored as HSV codes. These values were manually retrieved for use in QGIS.

Recreating the style in QGIS

QGIS accepts colour entries in various formats, including RGB, hue, lightness, saturation (HLS) and HSV codes. The extracted HSV values were used directly to create a continuous colour ramp with the Style Manager tool (fig. 4).

The new colour ramp was then applied to a bathymetric grid, with the corresponding hillshade grid layered on top. To replicate the NOAA NCEI style accurately, the styles of both the bathymetric grid and the hillshade layer had to be adjusted in tandem, as they together form the complete style. Independently they do not achieve the desired effect. Due to limitations in GeoServer and the SLD format, only certain styling settings were available. The final style was refined by adjusting transparency, saturation, and blending mode.

Exporting and Implementing Styles in GeoServer

After finalizing the style in QGIS, the styles for both the bathymetry grid and hillshade grid were exported as SLD files. These encapsulated the visual parameters of the style, such as colour ramps and transparency (referred to as opacity in SLD). However, the blending mode (referred to as composite in SLD) had to be added manually due to lack of support. To address the absence of support for saturation in GeoServer and the SLD format, python scripting was used to convert the hex colour codes to RGB, then to HLS, where the saturation value was adjusted to 80%. The modified values were converted back to hex format and incorporated into the final SLD file. A python code example can be found in the appendices.

The final step involved uploading the modified SLD files to GeoServer, where the styles were applied to the corresponding image mosaic layers.

Discussions

Challenges with ArcGIS Pro style extraction

Extracting and exporting styles from ArcGIS Pro posed a significant challenge due to the limited compatibility with open-source software like QGIS or GeoServer. In ArcGIS Pro, styles need to be

Figure 4: Colour ramp creation with the QGIS' Style Manager

saved as a raster function template, which is then exported as an XML file. This file can be opened by various programs, but it contains more than just symbology information. The colours, in the form of HSV codes, had to be manually retrieved for further use.

For future applications, this process could be automated with a script to streamline the extraction of the HSV values. Automating the extraction would significantly reduce the manual effort and improve the efficiency of the workflow, especially when handling multiple styles.

Differences between using a raster layer group and a single RGB raster

A key difference between the approach used for this workflow and that of NOAA NCEI's Multibeam Bathymetry Mosaic is the way layers are structured. In the case of NOAA NCEI' image service, an RGB raster is used, whereas, in this project, two layers — bathymetry and hillshade — were used and combined into a GeoServer layer group.

Using a layer group has several advantages: styles can be modified independently for each layer, while the underlying data (e.g., elevation values) remain accessible. This allows for greater flexibility when working with the layers, as changes can be made without affecting the underlying data. On the other hand, an RGB raster has limitations as its style cannot be easily adjusted once applied. Additionally, the pixel value only represents the RGB colour code. The original underlying information is lost.

Gaining an understanding of the NOAA NCEI's workflow for creating the RGB raster and styling was essential for adapting their visual style to the bathymetry and hillshade layers in this project.

Limitations in GeoServer and SLD format

The GeoServer and SLD format introduced several limitations that hindered the seamless transfer of styles from QGIS. While QGIS supports a variety of advanced rendering features, such as saturation, brightness, and gamma adjustments, these features are not fully supported in the SLD format or by GeoServer.

GeoServer supports both SLD 1.0 and 1.1, but QGIS uses the older version, SLD 1.0, for exporting styles. This version mismatch leads to certain limitations, as some styling options available in QGIS are not supported by the SLD 1.0 format or are handled differently in GeoServer. Notably, the ability to handle blending modes was introduced in SLD 1.1, which was not available in the 1.0 specification. As a result, the blending mode had to be manually added to the exported SLD file.

The table below summarizes the support for various styling features across QGIS, SLD 1.0, and SLD 1.1:

	QGIS	SLD 1.0	SLD 1.1
Blending Mode	x	-	x (not all)
Brightness	x	-	-
Contrast	x	-	-
Gamma	x	-	x (different to QGIS)
Saturation	x	-	-
Transparency	x	x	x

In addition to the blending mode, certain settings such as brightness, gamma, contrast, and saturation are either not supported or handled differently in SLD 1.1. The gamma value in SLD version 1.1 adjusts the brightness and contrast of the raster. Below, a comparison of the gamma effect is shown

with a value of 0.6. Figure 5 shows on the left the QGIS version and on the right the GeoServer version, which appears much lighter.

Figure 5: Comparing gamma value in QGIS (left) and GeoServer (right). The background raster is NOAA NCEI's Multibeam Bathymetry Mosaic⁵

In particular, GeoServer does not support direct saturation adjustments in the SLD format. This required an additional workaround with python scripting as mentioned in chapter "Exporting and Implementing Styles in GeoServer".

Despite these limitations, transparency was successfully retained across both versions, allowing for some consistency between QGIS and GeoServer.

Colour Code Conversion

The conversion process between colour formats introduced complexity, particularly when adjusting saturation. Although the HSV codes from the ArcGIS raster function template could have been used directly, it turned out that working with the hex codes was more efficient. Hex codes were easily extractable from the SLD file, allowing for quicker adjustments than dealing with the RGB or HSV codes.

The process followed these steps:

1. Convert the hex colour codes to RGB.
2. Convert the RGB values to HLS.
3. Adjust the saturation in HLS.
4. Convert the modified HLS values back to hex.

This process required careful attention to ensure that the final colours remained visually consistent with the QGIS style, as even small changes in the saturation could alter the appearance of the map layers. The final hex values were then incorporated into the SLD file, allowing the same style to be applied in GeoServer.

⁵https://gis.ngdc.noaa.gov/arcgis/rest/services/multibeam_mosaic/ImageServer

Consistency across layers

Ensuring visual consistency across the bathymetry and hillshade layers was one of the most critical aspects of the workflow. The final style was not a simple combination of two independently styled layers but rather the result of fine-tuning both layers to work in harmony.

Both the bathymetry and hillshade layers needed to be adjusted together to create a coherent visual representation. The interaction between the two layers' styles was crucial, as the final visual output depended on how the colours, transparency, and blending modes from each layer work in combination. Therefore, the styling process involved iteratively adjusting of both layers to match the intended visual look of NOAA NCEI's image service.

This dual-layer approach emphasized the importance of the coordination between the bathymetry grid and the hillshade grid. Each layer contributed to the final output, but neither layer could stand alone in replicating the desired result. The visual interaction between these two layers was essential for producing the accurate representation of the bathymetric data.

Conclusion

This workflow successfully demonstrated the process of transferring and adapting QGIS styles to GeoServer, despite several challenges posed by the limitations of the SLD format and GeoServer's support for advanced rendering features. Through a series of workarounds, including manual adjustments to blending modes and saturation, the visual integrity of the bathymetry and hillshade layers was preserved, closely matching the NOAA NCEI style. While certain style parameters were unsupported or handled differently in GeoServer, the project highlighted the importance of understanding both platforms' workflows and the need for flexibility when working with raster styles across different systems. Overall, the approach outlined provides valuable insights for future integration efforts involving QGIS, GeoServer, and the SLD format.

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⁶<https://datahub.erde-und-umwelt.de>

Appendices

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research (Alfred-Wegener-Institut, Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung)
CIRES	Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences
DCDB	Data Centre for Digital Bathymetry
HLS	Hue, Lightness, Saturation (colour model)
HSV	Hue, Saturation, Value (colour model)
IHO	International Hydrographic Organization
NCEI	National Centers for Environmental Information
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OWS	OGC Web Services
RGB	Red-Green-Blue (colour model)
SLD	Styled Layer Descriptor
WMS	Web Map Service

Python code for colour code conversion

```

1  # -*- coding: utf-8 -*-
2
3  """
4  This script takes a hex colour code as input and then converts it to RGB
   and then to HLS, adjusts the saturation (S value) and converts it
   back to RGB and then to hex.
5  hex > RGB > HLS > adjust S > HLS > RGB > hex
6  It was used to adjust the saturation of a GeoServer colour ramp, because
   there is no setting to adjust the saturation directly in the
   GeoServer.
7  """
8
9  import colorsys
10
11 # Variables:
12 ds = 0.20
13 hex = "#60e2f0"
14
15 # Convert hex color to RGB.
16 # The first two characters of the hex code representing the red
   component, the middle two representing the green component, and the
   last two representing the blue component. The int() function is used
   to convert the extracted two-character substring (e.g., "0a", "00",
   "78") to an integer using base 16 (hexadecimal).
17 # Example: hex code "#0a0078" --> r = 10, g = 0, b = 120
18 r, g, b = tuple(int(hex[i:i + 2], 16) for i in (1, 3, 5))
19
20 # Convert RGB to HSL.
21 # The function expects the RGB components to be in the range of 0 to 1,
   therefore divide by 255.

```

```

22 # Example: r = 10/255.0, g = 0/255.0, b = 120/255.0 --> h =
    0.6805555555555555, l = 0.23529411764705882, s = 1.0
23 h, l, s = colorsys.rgb_to_hls(r / 255.0, g / 255.0, b / 255.0)
24
25 # Reduce the saturation by -20%
26 # Example: s = 1.0 --> s = 0.8
27 s = max(0, min(1, s - ds))
28
29 # Convert back to RGB.
30 # Example: h = 0.6805555555555555, l = 0.23529411764705882, s = 0.9 -->
    r = 20, g = 12, b = 108
31 r, g, b = tuple(round(val * 255) for val in colorsys.hls_to_rgb(h, l, s)
    )
32
33 # Convert RGB to hex
34 # Example: r = 20, g = 12, b = 108 --> #140c6c
35 new_color_hex = "#{:02x}{:02x}{:02x}".format(r, g, b)
36
37 print(new_color_hex)

```

Files included in Zenodo publication

- NCEI_haxby.xml - QGIS colour ramp file
- ncei_haxby_sat80.sld - Colour ramp style for GeoServer
- hillshade_new.sld - Hillshade style for GeoServer

References

- Crameri, Fabio, Grace E. Shephard, and Philip J. Heron. 2020. "The Misuse of Colour in Science Communication." *Nature Communications* 11(1):5444. doi: 10.1038/s41467-020-19160-7.
- Gołębiowska, Izabela, and Arzu Çöltekin. 2022. "What's Wrong with the Rainbow? An Interdisciplinary Review of Empirical Evidence for and Against the Rainbow Color Scheme in Visualizations." *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing* 194:195–208. doi: 10.1016/j.isprs.2022.10.002.
- GRASS Development Team. 2009. "GRASS Colour Ramps."
- Wessel, Paul, Walter Smith, and Andreas Trawoeger. 2012. "Generic Mapping Tools Palettes."